

Analysis of FDI - Indian Context

M.Rajakumari

Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce

R.D.Government Arts College, Sivagangai, Tamilnadu

Abstract

This paper attempted to make a diagnostic of FDI in India. India has already marked its presence as one of the best ever growing economies of the global. It has been ranked among the top ten attractive destinations for inbound investments. Since 1991, the regulatory environment in terms of foreign investment has been always eased to make it investor-friendly. The measures taken by the Government are directed to open new sectors for foreign direct investment, increase the pectoral limit of existing sectors and simplifying other conditions of the FDI policy. FDI policy reforms are meant to provide ease of doing business and accelerate the pace of foreign investment in the country. The following are the objectives of the prospective study. To study the new FDI policy in India and Cumulative FDI inflows in to India, to Find the cumulative FDI inflows in to India during the period 2000 - 2017, to analysis of Route Wise FDI inflows in India, and to analysis the current scenario of share of top investing countries.

Keywords: FDI, DIPP, UNCTA, DATA, BOP, FIPB, FII

Introduction

Indian Economy has been still considered as capital is needed to development and builds the economy of our nation. Hence, a high level of economic growth is not sustainable. At this juncture foreign direct investment is widely recognized as important drive of growth in our country. Foreign direct investment (FDI) being a non – debt capital flow, is a leading source of external financing, especially for the developing economies. It not only brings in capital and technical know- how but also increase the competitiveness of the economy. Over all its supplements domestic investment, much required for sustaining the high growth rate of the country. Indian Economy is still considered capital scared one. We need long term capital to develop and build the economy. Foreign direct investment (FDI) plays an important role in the developing economy like India. The polices relating foreign direct investment(FDI) Underwent a major change in July 1991 as a part of the structural adjustment programme in India, under the P.V. Narasima Rao led congress Government. In this paper roll of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in retail sector, FDI Equity Inflow, sector wise FDI inflows in India and share of

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 7

Special Issue : 1

Month : February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Rajakumari, M.

“Analysis of FDI -

Indian Context.” *Shanlax*

International Journal of

Commerce, vol. 7,

no. S1, 2019, pp. 116–

122.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2552230)

[zenodo.2552230](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2552230)

top investing countries FDI inflows in India. Since 1991, the regulatory environment for foreign investment has consistently been eased to make it investor-friendly, catapulting India into the position of one of the fastest-growing economies of the world. It has been ranked (9th in terms of FDI inflows for 2016 by UNCTAD) among the top attractive destinations for inbound investments in the world. The Government of India with intent to attract and promote Foreign Direct Investment has put in place a policy framework on Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) which is transparent, predictable and easily comprehensible. Foreign investment into an Indian entity on a strategic basis is subject to FDI policy. The (Government of India) through Department of Industrial Policy & Promotion (DIPP) formulates a consolidated FDI Policy on a yearly basis which is a defined framework for FDI. Currently, the FDI policy of 28 August 2017 is in effect.

FDI is not permitted in the Following Industrial Sectors

Arm and Ammunition, Atomic Energy, Railway Transport, Coal and lignite, Mining Of Iron, Manganese, Chrome ,Gypsum, Gold, Diamonds, Copper, Zinc, Lottery Business, Gambling And Betting, Business Of Chit Fund, Agriculture, Housing And Real Estate Business And Trading In Transferable Developments Rights.

Operational Definitions

Flows of FDI

FDI has three components like as equity capital, reinvested earnings and intra company loans.

Inward FDI

Inward FDI occurs when foreign capital is invested in local resources which include tax breaks, low interest rates and grants.

Outward FDI

Outward FDI also referred to as direct investment abroad is backed by the government against all associated risk.

Financial Year

The financial year starts from 1st April of every year and ends on 31st March of the subsequent year.

Review of Literature

Renju Joseph (2018) Discussed the Impact of FDI Inflows in Balance of Payment. He has main objective of the study is to show the relation current account and balance of trade and capital accountant FDI and how its effect on balance of payment of country. The concluded that there is a significant association of current account to the balance of trade with beta value as 1.04, regression value is 0.987 with significance value 0.000 this implies that the balance of trade has a strong impact of current account. Currently the current account is deficit but on a declining mode. Balance of trade having a strong association can be used as a major tool to control the deficit and decrees the deficit. D.Rmamesh &S. Packialakshmi (2014), in their paper namely “the pros and cons of foreign direct investment in India” In this study concluded that in India is need to put in place a comprehensive development strategy, which includes being open to trade and FDI. This should go a long way in fulfilling that the ultimate goal of permanently eradicating poverty. Boopath (2013) revealed that the Press Council of India has commented on synergic alliance or equity participation by way of Foreign Direct Investment. The council opined that Foreign Direct Investment should be allowed to break or halt the growing monopoly of a few media giants in India who offer uneven playground and unhealthy competition to small and medium industry. Narayana

(2012) explained that one of the major concerns of planners and policy makers in India is attracting more and more Foreign Direct Investment. He analyzed the Foreign Direct Investment and its flows into India. He highlighted the basic constraints to investment in general and Foreign Direct Investment in particular.

Objective of the Study

The following are the objectives of the prospective study.

- To study the new FDI policy in India and Cumulative FDI inflows in to India.
- To find the cumulative FDI inflows in to India during the period 2000 - 2017
- To analysis of Route Wise FDI inflows in India.
- To analysis of Country wise FDI inflows in India during April 2015 to September 2017

Methodology

Type of research: - Quantitative and Analytical Research.

Data collection method: - secondary data different websites and reports of RBI.

Period of the Study

In this paper, the study period covers 12 financial years' starts from April 2000 and ends with September 2017.

Limitation of the Study

In the present analysis only a few parameters have been studied; the study fully based on the secondary dada only. As such the data are taken from the RBI reports, the analysis is based on the rendered information from the institutions alone and the suggestions rendered may not be extended to the similar type of organization.

New FDI Policy in 2017

The ability to attract large scale Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) into India has been a key driver for policy making by the Government. Prime Minister Modi seems to be going along the right track, with India receiving FDI inflows worth USD 60.1 billion in 2016-17, which was an all-time high. Hence, the FDI policy of India has always been closely watched and carefully amended over the years. On August 28th, 2017, the Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion (DIPP) had issued the updated and revised Foreign Direct Investment Policy, 2017 – 2018 (FDI Policy 2017). The FDI Policy 2017 incorporated various notifications issued by the Government of India over the past year.

Table 1 Foreign Direct Investment Limit for the Year

S.No	Sectors	FDI Limit % Previous Year - 2017	FDI Limit in % 2018
1	Banking Sector	74	100
2	Aviation	49	100
3	Investment In Single Brand Retail	-	100
4	Construction	49	100
5	Power Exchange	49	100
6	Medical Device	49	100
7	Defense	49	100

8	Insurance, Pension, Other Financial Service, Trading ,Etc.	-	51
9	Asset Reconstruction Companies	-	100
10	Pharmaceuticals	-	100
11	Broadcasting	-	100

Source: Cabinet Approves Amendments in FDI Policy. 12-1-2018

Table 2 Cumulative FDI inflows in to India during the period 2000 - 2017

S.No	Particulars	Amount of FDI inflows	
		Rs.	US \$ million
1	Cumulative FDI inflows (2000-2017)	-	5,18,100
2	Cumulative FDI equity inflow(2000-2017)	Rs.19,50,051 Crore	3,57,345
3	Amount of FDI equity inflows during the financial year 2017-18	Rs.95,942 Crore	14,946
4	Amount of Total equity inflows during the financial year 2017-2018	-	19,047

Source: Fact sheet FDI. RBI April 2000 - September2017

Table II depicts that the amount of FDI inflows from April 2000 to September 2017. It shows the cumulative amount of FDI inflows both in terms of crore and US \$ million. The first part shows the sum of equity inflows, reinvested earnings and other capital. Cumulative amount of inflows are 5,18,100 in US \$ million. Other then this cumulative FDI equity inflows which excludes amount remitted through RBI s NRI schemes are 19,50,051 in crore and 3,57,345 in US \$ million, FDI inflows during 2017-2018 (September- 2017) the first part shows the sum of equity inflows, reinvested earnings and other capital. The total amount of inflows are 19.047 in US \$ million. The second part shows that the FDI equity inflows amounted 95,942 in crore and 14,946 in US \$million.

Table 3 Route Wise FDI inflows in India during 2008-09 (April) to 2017-2018 (September)

(Amount Rupees in Crores)

S.No	Year	Government Route / FIPB / RBI Acquisition Route	Equity	Reinvested earnings	Other Capital	Total FDI inflow
1	2008-09	31,364	702	9,032	776	41,874
2	2009-10	25,606	1,540	8,668	1,931	37,745
3	2010-11	21,376	874	11,939	658	34,847
4	2011-12	34,833	1,022	8,206	24,995	46,556
5	2012-2013	21,825	1,059	9,880	1,534	34,298
6	2013-2014	24,299	975	8,978	1,794	36,046

7	2014-2015(p)	30,933	978	9,988	3,249	45,148
8	2015-2016(P)	40,001	1,111	10,413	4,034	55,559
9	2016-2017(P)	43,478	1,227	12,176	3,201	60,082
10	2017-2018(P) Up to sep- 2017	25,354	542	5,792	2,060	33,749
11	TOTAL	2,99,069	10,030	95,072	44,232	4,25,904
12	CAGR%	-2.155%	-2.55%	-44.34%	10.26%	87.91%
13	MEAN	29,907	1,003	9,507	4,423	42,590.4
14	SD	7,618	274	1,947	7,286	13,398.14
15	CV	25.47	27.30	20.48	164.73	31.458

Source: Reserve Bank of India, FIPB: Foreign Investment Promotion Board, Bulletin, April – 2017 (Fact Sheet FDI 2000 – 2017)

The above table III reveals route wise FDI inflows in India during the year 2008-2009 to 2017-2018 (up to September 2017), the mean of government route/FIPB/acquisition route is having highest route wise FDI of 29.907 and lowest mean of 4.423 followed by other capital, the compound annual growth rate of route wise FDI was only positive in the case of other capital (10.26%) and remaining was negative route wise FDI.

**Table 4 Country Wise Fdi Inflows In India During April 2015 To September 2017
(Amount Rupees In Crores (Us \$ Million))**

Ranks	Country	2015-2016 April- March	2016-17 April- March	2017-18 April- September	MEAN	SD	CV	CAGR%
1.	Mauritius	54,706 (83,55)	1,05,587 (5,728)	73,589 (11,466)	77,961	25,721	32.99	10.39
2.	Singapore	89,510 (13,692)	58,376 (8,711)	34,105 (5,294)	60,664	27,773	45.78	-27.5
3.	Japan	17,275 (2,614)	31,588 (4,709)	6,118 (950)	18,327	12,768	69.66	-29.25
4.	U.K	5,938 (898)	9,953 (1,483)	1,920 (298)	5,937	9,419	158.64	-31.36
5.	Netherlands'	17,275 (2,643)	22,633 (3,367)	12,526 (1,945)	17,478	5,057	28.93	-10.16
6.	USA	27,695 (4,192)	15,957 (2,379)	8,544 (1,327)	17,399	96,576	55.50	-32.43
7.	Germany	6,361 (986)	7,175 (1,069)	6,020 (934)	6,519	593	9.10	-1.82
8.	Cyprus	3,317 (508)	4,050 (604)	1,429 (222)	2,932	1,352	46.12	-24.47
9.	France	3,937 (598)	4,112 (614)	1,962 (305)	3,337	1,194	35.78	-20.72
10.	U.A.E.	6,528 (985)	4,539 (675)	1,581 (245)	4,216	2,489	59.04	-37.67

	Total FDI Inflows	2,62,322 (40,001)	2,91,696 (3,478)	1,63,028 (25,354)				-14.66
	MEAN	2,6232	2,9170	16,303				
	SD	26,803	32,718	22,932				
	C.V	102.17	112.16	1.41				

Source: www.dipp.gov/fdi-statisticatilfigure-FDI April 2015 to September 2017

The above table IV shows the mean country wise FDI inflows in India Mauritius is fluctuating trend during the study period highest mean of (77,961) and Cyprus has the lowest mean of (2,932). The compound annual growth rate of country wise FDI inflow was positive in the case of Mauritius (10.29%) and the rest of the country it is negative during the period.

Findings of the Study

On the basis of present study the finding are

1. FDI is an important stimulus for the economic growth of India.
2. The foreign investment increased in the terms of FDI.
3. cumulative FDI equity inflows which excludes amount remitted through RBI s NRI schemes are Rs, 19,50,051 in crore and 3,57,345 in US \$ million.
4. The highest amount 11,466 million dollars of FDI in India came from Mauritius and Singapore has second and USA has six places.
5. FDI create high perks jobs for skilled and semi skilled employee in Indian service sector.
6. As per RBI study group from the DIPP- financial year wise FDI equity inflows perspective in the year 2016-17 Rs, 2,91,696 crores (43,478 us\$ million) and followed by 2015-2016 Rs.2,62,322 crore (40,001 us \$ million).
7. The compound annual growth rate of route wise FDI was only positive in the case of other capital (10.26%).
8. As per RBI examine group from the FDI Equity inflow month wise report august, 2017. Rs.51,198 crore (8004 US\$ million) and followed by July, 2017 Rs 31,112 crore (4,827 us \$ million).

Conclusions

In India FDI plays a pivotal role in Indian economy through its constitution to transfer of knowledge and improvement of technologies create employment through the development of different regions. The Government of India is recently increased the limit of FDI in different sector. However there are many obstacle in the way of FDI inflow and dominate in the majority National ruling party. Government should take final decision in the field of FDI in particular sector cannot construe in other ruling party. If above pointed out done on a priority basis FDI will be import role in the development of our country. This paper focuses on theoretical aspects of FDI in India during the last ten years, determinants and need of FDI in Indian scenario. India has been one of the developing countries and has managed to show a positive GDP growth even during the recession period. It has comparatively performed well, then the average growth rate of world GDP.

References

- Boopath, D “Foreign Direct Investment in Print Media” Foreign Direct Investment and Financial Crisis(Ed.), *New Century Publications New Delhi*, 2013, pp.29-41
- Fact sheet FDI. RBI April 2000 - September2017.
<http://www.makeinindia.com/policy/foreign-direct-investment>

Narayana, N “Foreign Direct Investment in India; Constraints and the Need for Suitable Measures” Foreign Investment and Indian Economy (Ed), *Manglam Publishers & Distributors*, Delhi, 2012.

Renju Joseph, “The Impact of Foreign Direct Investment Inflows in Balance of Payment,” *International Journal of Research in Commerce, Economics and Management*, vol.8, no.63, 2018, ISSN -2231-4245.

Rmamesh. D & Packialakshmi, S 2014, “The Pros and Cons of Foreign Direct Investment in India,” *Fact For You*, 2014. pp13-17.

<https://corporate.cyrilamarchandblogs.com/2017/09/india-announces-new-foreign-direct-investment-policy-2017-2018>.

<https://www.investindia.gov.in/foreign-direct-investment>

www.dipp.gov/fdi-statisticatilfigure-India - FDI April 2015 to September 2017.